

DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTH INSURANCE

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Annotation: In the article Medical Aid creating an acceptable organizational structure and model of financial support of the tax saving sector.

Key words: public health, medical care, health care, financing of tax care, medical assistance, paid medical service.

The most important element of the social, cultural and economic development of the state is the health, quality and standard of living indicators of the population. Nevertheless, the budgetary model of financing the health sector, due to the lack of allocated funds, does not satisfy the needs of the population for the guaranteed volume of free medical care, as defined by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. There is a need to replace free medical care with paid services due to the lack of a clear distinction between the guaranteed volume of medical care provided to citizens on a paid basis and medical services.

The level and importance of insurance protection of the population is determined by personal factors, systemic changes in the economic and political plan, natural-geographical, cultural-historical characteristics of the country. In the period of economic problems and increasing social tensions, the need for its expansion and improvement becomes the most urgent and important. In the event of an insurance event, insurance protection of individuals and legal entities by insurance companies should be divided as follows, depending on the type of insurance

Insurance protection has a social orientation, because the funds collected by the insurer are directed to the protection of victims at the expense of all participants in the formation of the insurance fund. Insurance aims to meet the various needs of mankind in the event of adverse events leading to various losses through the insurance protection system. Society's interest in continuous and continuous production increases its interest in insurance protection.

The most important aspect of social protection of the population is to ensure the availability of medical care. In this area, health insurance is an alternative financing method for the market economy.

The object of medical insurance is the risk of loss of income of the working-age population and the risks of additional costs associated with receiving medical care.

The purpose of health insurance is to guarantee the financing of medical care and preventive measures to the population in the event of an insured event.

Medical insurance forms

Signs	Medical insurance forms	
	Compulsory health insurance (MTS)	Voluntary health insurance (ITS)
Reflects the attitude to the social insurance	An integral part of the state social insurance, which provides equal opportunities for the population to receive medical care at the expense of compulsory medical	Obtaining additional medical services (type of private insurance) in addition to the mandatory health insurance (MTS) program by attracting free funds of enterprises and citizens to the health

system	insurance	sector.
Legal framework	It is promulgated and regulated by laws and regulations on compulsory insurance and state extra-budgetary funds.	It is regulated by laws on insurance and commercial organizations based on the voluntary consent of the parties involved in insurance.
Insurance periods	Without a deadline	Limited by insurance contract
Signs	Medical insurance forms	
	Compulsory health insurance (MTS)	Voluntary health insurance (ITS)
Source of funding	Compulsory payments (employers' and working-age population's contributions), budget subsidies	Voluntary contributions of citizens and legal entities from the income or benefits they receive
Calculation of insurance premium	It is determined simultaneously with the approval of the state budget by the legislative body	Statistical data on the occurrence of relevant insurance events (list of risks, program level, number of insured persons, service area, health status of the insured person and usually determined after medical examination) is voluntarily produced by the insurer.
Principles	Universality, statehood, non-commercial character, obligation	discretion, convenience
Insurers	State (local executive authorities), employers, employees	Legal and natural persons
The insured	All citizens	The limited number of citizens associated with the desire (possibility) to participate in this form of insurance
Insurers	Centralized social health insurance fund	Insurance organizations of different forms of ownership
Scope of medical care and services	The same amount of guaranteed and state-defined medical services for all	Additional volume of medical services, expansion of opportunities for providing medical care in terms of volume and quality

As a result of the analysis of different approaches to the study of insurance functions, we identify the following as the main functions of health insurance: risk, compensation, social and national income redistribution functions and protection to additional functions, prevention of unpleasantness, control, accumulation, investment, demographic, stabilization, etc. includes functions

Thus, from the point of view of public health protection, the role of health insurance as an important element of social protection is determined by the conditions of health care financing, which depends on the quality of medical services provided. In this regard, it is necessary to introduce medical insurance activities in order to increase the quality of

insurance services provided in the medical insurance market, to provide effective development and financing of the health care sector in order to receive the necessary medical assistance in case of illness.

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